

GHRSSST

*Group for High Resolution
Sea Surface Temperature*

The Group for High Resolution Sea Surface
Temperature

User Requirements

GHRSSST Science Team
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Version 1.0

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the Document

The aim of the URD is to describe the SST products, services and additional information the large variety of users requires for their applications.

As GHRSSST service providers are not funded through GHRSSST but through a wide range of national and international bodies, this URD can only be considered as advisory, not mandatory for GHRSSST members.

1.2 Reference Documents

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[CCI] ESA CCI Phase 1 (SST) User requirements document. SST_CCI-URD-Issue_2.pdf, Nov 2010. UKMO-001-

[MUR] Medspiration User Requirement Document (URD) v2.6.doc, June 2003.

[NAS] Sea Surface Temperature Error Budget: White Paper NASA Interim Sea Surface Temperature Science Team (ISSTST) http://www.ssterrorbudget.org/ISSTST/White_Paper.html, June 2010.

[OSP] OSISAF CDOP Product Requirement Document SAF/OSI/CDOP/M-September 2009. F/MGT/PL/001,

[OSS] OSISAF CDOP Service Specification Document. SAF/OSI/CDOP/M-February 2010. F/MGT/PL/003,

[OUS] Australian Government, Bureau of Meteorology, Oceanographic Services Survey Report 2011. User

[PMD] GHRSSST SST definition discussions <https://www.ghrsst.org/files/download.php?m=documents&f=120113121306-SSTDefinitionsDiscussion.pdf>

[UGU] GHRSSST User Guide <https://www.ghrsst.org/files/download.php?m=documents&f=111020110451-GHRSSSTUserGuidev91.pdf>

Amarasekera, N.A., R.F. Lee, E.R. Williams, and E.A.B. Eltahir. (1998): ENSO and the natural variability in the flow of tropical rivers. *J. of Hydrology*, 200, 24-39. It is well recognised that SST has predictive skill for river flood forecasting. E.g., Egypt depends on the Nile River for all of its water resources.

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Giannini A., Biasutti, M. Held, I. M. and Sobel A.H.(2008): *Climatic Change*, [Volume 90, Number 4](#) (2008), 359-383, DOI: 10.1007/s10584-008-9396-y.

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Koegeler and Dahle (1991): *Arctic* 44, supp. 1, 34-39.

Kusuma, D.W. and Jatisworo, D. (2011), *Proceedings of the 2ND CReSOS Symposium, Bali-Inonesia, 21-22 Feb 2011*).

Ohring G., Wielicki B., Spencer R., Emery B., and Datla R. (2005): *Satellite Instrument Calibration for Measuring Global Climate Change: Report of a Workshop*. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **86**, 1303-1313.

Rasmusson, E.M., and T.H. Carpenter. (1983). The relationship between eastern equatorial Pacific sea surface temperatures and rainfall over India and Srilanka. *Mon. Weather Rev.* 111, 517-528.

1.3 Relevant Web sites

- [URL-1] <https://www.ghrsst.org>
- [URL-2] <http://www.wmo-sat.info/db/variables/view/134>
- [URL-3] <https://www.ghrsst.org/users-partners/quick-start/>
- [URL-4] <https://www.ghrsst.org/users-partners/user-requirements/>
- [URL-5] <https://www.ghrsst.org/users-partners/applications/applications-in-nwp/>
- [URL-6] <https://www.ghrsst.org/users-partners/applications/ocean-forecasting/>
- [URL-7] http://wind.mit.edu/~emanuel/Papers_data_graphics.htm
- [URL-8] <http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/tropicalcyclone/seasonal/northatlantic2011>
- [URL-9] <http://ess.uci.edu/5311/feature-randers>
- [URL-10] http://www.iucn.org/cccr/resilience_to_climate_change/
- [URL-11] <http://www.seasurface.com>
- [URL-12] <http://www.seaviewfishing.com/>
- [URL-13] <http://www.fishtrack.com/>
- [URL-14] <http://bangordailynews.com/2012/03/13/news/state/coast-guard-warns-boaters-of-deadly-winter-like-water-temperatures/>
- [URL-15] <http://www.eea.europa.eu/atlas/eea/eco-tourism/satellite-images/satellite-images/turkey-sea-surface-temperature-sst/view>

2 GHRSSST User Communities

Applications that benefit from satellite SST products cover the full range of temporal and spatial scales. Time scales associated with ocean processes include diurnal, multi-day, intraseasonal, seasonal, annual, interannual, decadal, and longer-term trends. Associated spatial scales cover the full range - from the meter to the global scale. Phenomena and processes include: the diurnal warming and cooling cycle; surface expression of internal waves; regional air-sea interaction processes including synoptic events, intraseasonal processes (especially in the tropical and coastal regions), fluxes near fronts, and convection and mixing in mode and deep water formation regions; open ocean fronts; regional to basin-scale fluxes of heat, evaporation, and precipitation associated with the seasonal cycle, trade wind, and monsoon regimes; seasonal to interannual basin and global-scale processes such as ENSO; decadal variability such as the PDO; and global change-induced trends. For the coastal regions (and in lakes) applications include: upwelling, sub-mesoscale eddies and fronts, jets and filaments, and the impact of biogeochemical, pollutant and river inflow processes on both dynamics and optical properties. In many cases the effects of coastal processes extend well offshore and influence open ocean conditions. In addition to covering the full range of spatial and temporal scales, the phenomena and processes have associated space/time signatures and amplitudes that vary regionally.

Consequently, Sea Surface temperature (SST) is of interest for many user communities:

- Aquaculture
- Atmospheric research
- Aviation
- Climate variability and change
- Coastal users (recreational and coast guard)
- Commercial shipping
- Coral reef protection
- Ecosystems
- Fisheries
- Habitats
- Hazardous spill mitigation
- Hurricane research
- Media (TV, Film, News)
- Naval operations
- Ocean forecasting
- Ocean research
- Power plant outflow monitoring
- Recreational boating
- Recreational fishing
- Sailing and Racing
- Search and Rescue
- Seasonal Forecasting
- Teleconnection studies
- Tourism
- Weather Forecasting

In the next section, we present some example applications across five primary domains.

3 Applications of satellite SSTs

3.1 Operational Forecasting

The knowledge of the three-dimensional structure of the oceans requires the combined use of satellite observations, in-situ observations and ocean numerical models through assimilation techniques. Due to the limitations in coverage regarding the in-situ measurements, and the systematic errors in Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models, observations are required for Sea Surface Temperature (SST), radiative short-wave and long-wave fluxes. Together with near-surface wind vectors and ice cover observations, these parameters can be used for the modelling of heat and momentum exchange. Such a coherent set of information can then be used for characterizing the ocean surface and the energy fluxes through it.

3.2 Numerical Weather Prediction

Numerical weather prediction uses current weather conditions as input into mathematical models of the atmosphere to predict the weather. Sea surface temperature and sea-ice affect the behaviour of the overlying atmosphere and vice versa. Consequently, NWP systems need to be regularly updated with the latest SST and sea-ice observations to ensure an accurate forecast. Daily analyses of both SST and sea-ice extent and concentration are required by many operational NWP systems. SST affects the formation and subsequent evolution of tropical cyclones, convection and thunderstorms, cyclogenesis, sea fog and sea breezes. It can also help upper air forecasters at the World Aviation Forecast Centre to monitor areas more likely to develop Cumulonimbus activity which can produce significant threat to aircraft.

3.2.1 Ocean Forecasting

Operational numerical prediction ocean model systems providing forecasts of currents, temperature and salinity fields are used for a variety of operational applications including coral reef management, tide predictions, marine sanctuary and estuary management, diving operations, naval applications, oil and chemical spill drift forecasts, search and rescue operations, offshore oil drilling operations, cable laying and ship routing. Today, a dozen numerical ocean modelling systems routinely operate in the nine countries that participated in the Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment (GODAE) (Dombrowsky et al. 2009). They range from regional high resolution systems that include tides, to global eddy-resolving systems that provide estimates of the ocean state, updated regularly (from daily to monthly), providing forecasts from a few days to one month ahead (Dombrowsky et al. 2009; <https://www.godae-oceanview.org/>).

3.2.2 Seasonal and Interannual Forecasting

Several operational centres routinely issue seasonal forecasts of the Earth's climate using coupled ocean-atmosphere models, which require near-real-time knowledge of the state of the global ocean (Balmaseda et al. 2009). Seasonal forecasting systems are based on coupled ocean-atmosphere general circulation models that predict SSTs and their impact on atmospheric circulation. The aim of seasonal forecasts is to predict climate anomalies (e.g. temperature, rainfall, frequency of tropical cycles) for the forthcoming seasons (Balmaseda et al. 2009). The strongest relationship between SST patterns and seasonal weather trends are found in tropical regions.

3.3 Climate Monitoring and Research

3.3.1 Teleconnection studies

Teleconnection patterns relate the SST anomaly with anomalies in ocean currents, atmospheric circulation, and respective rainfall anomalies. SST related teleconnections include the El Niño/Southern Oscillation, the Madden-Julian Oscillation and with implications for the Monsoon, the Arctic/North Atlantic Oscillation, and the rainfall over large parts of the globe. Such large-scale climate anomalies have economic consequences for agriculture and fishing, and determine the severity or frequency of natural hazards such as tropical cyclones, droughts, floods and fires.

Monitoring long-term trends in SST observations of subsurface ocean temperature have been used to monitor long-term changes in the global SST since the late 1800's. However, these have been limited spatially, and available SST analyses of in situ data are of relatively coarse resolution, typically monthly on a 5-degree grid (e.g. HadSST2, ERSST v3). Since 1981, SST observations from infrared radiometers on polar-orbiting satellites have also been used to monitor multi-decadal trends (e.g. Reynolds et al., 2007). However, satellite SST data alone have not been used as a major resource for estimating climate change because of their strong time-varying biases which are hard to completely remove. Recent efforts by the ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) SST Project (<http://www.esa-sst-cci.org>) aim to produce a > 30-year satellite record of consistent SST at high spatial resolution (~ 5 km) with target accuracy of 0.1°C even in periods of elevated stratospheric aerosol.

3.4 Marine biology

Marine biology applications are especially interested in classifying habitats using SST, thus they need information about fronts, coastal areas and upwelling regions. They require information on effective feature resolution, and need to be warned of possible pitfalls in interpretation of areas with resolution changes. They need to be alerted to or provided with information concerning clouds, the possible linkage of clouds to fronts, as well as explanations about the technical cloud clearing information. Biology users might need some introduction about SST measured from space, and to be pointed to the concept of foundation temperature. They might benefit from using SST together with salinity.

3.4.1 Coral reefs

Coral bleaching results from the loss of symbiotic algae, known as zooxanthellae, from coral tissues during times of stress, often due to temperatures higher than the coral colony's tolerance level (Glynn, 1993). NOAA's Coral Reef Watch Program's satellite data provide current reef environmental conditions to quickly identify areas at risk for coral bleaching. Continuous monitoring of sea surface temperature at global scales provides researchers and stakeholders with tools to understand and better manage the complex interactions leading to coral bleaching. When bleaching conditions occur, these tools can be used to trigger bleaching response plans and support appropriate management decisions.

3.4.2 Fisheries

Different species of fish are sometimes known to be found at certain temperature ranges. Near real time SST maps derived from satellite data can help inform where good fishing locations might be (e.g. <http://www.fishtrack.com> and <https://www.satfish.com>). For example, SST is one of the most important environmental parameters used by longline fishermen to locate good fishing areas (Beverly, 2011). Pelagic fish such as albacore tuna (*Thunnus alalunga*), bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*), skipjack tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*), striped marlin (*Tetrapturus audax*), swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*), and yellowfin tuna (*Thunnus albacores*) have preferences for waters with certain temperature ranges. This is true for both horizontal and vertical temperature ranges, but longline fishermen are more interested in horizontal, or surface, temperatures when searching for fish (Beverly, 2011).

Frontal zones are also interesting to fishers because baitfish and predator fish often accumulate near them, often on the warm side of the frontal zone. In this case, the location of the front, rather than absolute temperature, is of greater interest to fishers.

3.5 Coastal and Inland waters

The application of SST products in coastal areas presents several issues. Coastal areas such as those off California and Peru have extended periods of times of cloud cover. Infrared sensors provide coverage at ~1 km, but cannot retrieve SSTs through clouds. Microwave sensors have all-weather capability (except for significant rain events), but are limited by their >25 km resolution. This can be limiting in applying SSTs in coastal areas where major upwelling events can occur in areas much closer than 25 km. Products should be developed that can combine SSTs from multiple sensors and produce reliable products at the 1 km resolutions required to study frontal structures in coastal areas. Such a global 1 km resolution gap-free SST analysis is

available from NASA JPL in the Multi-scale Ultra-high Resolution (MUR) daily SST analysis (<https://mur.jpl.nasa.gov>). This analysis has been assessed in highly dynamic coastal regions such as the Peruvian Coastal Upwelling System (Vazquez-Cuervo et al., 2013).

Cloud clearance and uncertainty information is particularly important to coastal and inland waters SST applications. Coastal users would benefit from an introduction to the microwave measurements. They need to apply the microwave data together with the appropriate land mask.

3.6 Recreational

3.6.1 Sailing/racing

Forecasts of ocean currents from general ocean circulation models can be very helpful to recreational boaters. Nowcasts of ocean currents can also be obtained from combining information about sea surface height anomaly from satellite altimeters with satellite SST data (e.g. <http://oceancurrent.imos.org.au>).

3.6.2 Surfing/swimming/diving

Observations and forecasts of SST can be helpful to recreational users who expect to immerse themselves in the ocean. However, as these in-water human activities generally occur in close proximity to the coast, it would be helpful to be able to quantify how accurate the high-resolution satellite SST analyses are within a few kilometres of land. Currently, commercial surfing information web sites such as Surfline (<http://www.surflin.com>) use the MUR 1 km gap-free SST analyses, based on infra-red and microwave satellite SST data, to provide SST information for recreational beach users.

4 Service requirements

Generally, users require:

- Guidance to find the most appropriate SST product. This includes not only specific parameters like resolution and coverage but also general product-type questions such as: whether L3 or L4 gridding is more appropriate for their applications, and whether they should use MW, IR or a combined-sensor product.
- File-format and Metadata specifications, which are necessities, but the issue here is delivery of such information. Complete manuals are often not accessible enough especially for the first-time users.
- Efficient data packaging and delivery which are issues with high resolution products which are usually large and becoming more common. A delivery system that allows the users to define which ancillary fields to download and subset these fields.
- Data mining and Software tools to locate and facilitate reading of the data. The benefit of standardization provided by the GHRSSST format is realized through these software tools - the interface between the users and products. Tools and services need to be implemented that allow for the extraction of large amounts of data over long time periods.
- Scientific advice which can be parts of "Guidance" above but also addresses issues of wider consequences such as: physical definition of "SST" and effects of physical processes and spatiotemporal variability on SST measurements.
- The power users as, e.g., weather services, require less guidance and scientific advice, but require operational information about technical details or changes in the processing, preferably with advance warning, and periods of overlap between different versions. The more advanced the user application, the more details about the data production are required, together with updates on the relevant developments in SST related science.
- On the other hand, a vast number of potentially new users of GHRSSST products are not power users. For example, field-scientists in developing countries may not have access to fast enough internet or large enough disk to take advantage of the high-resolution products, unless subsetting and time aggregation can be performed on the server side. Delivery software such as OPeNDAP may be able to address some of these for the gridded products but not yet for swathed products. Also, our delivery of the GHRSSST format specification to these potential users should be concise, direct, and accessible. We have an opportunity to educate these users to become advanced users. OPeNDAP needs to be combined with formats such as netCDF4 that allow for internal compression of data.

These service requirements are addressed by AUS-TAG and the GHRSSST Project Office. A primary point of contact is the web-site, the services of which are described in the next section.

4.1 User service requirements

Firstly, a user point of contact (web-site) and starting point for users is required: see <https://www.ghrsst.org/files/download.php?m=documents&f=110928144808-Onepagerinahurry.pdf>. This serves as a gateway for the initiated users to be introduced to the GHRSSST product collection, and "value-added" products such as the GHRSSST Multi-Product Ensemble (GMPE), and match-up data bases.

Next, general scientific information on the SST (including definitions) and on the scientific issues to consider is required. Thus, an explanation of the GHRSSST definitions [PMD] was prepared in 2011/2012 and provided via the website to the users <https://www.ghrsst.org/files/download.php?m=documents&f=120113121306-SSTDefinitionsDiscussion.pdf>.

This helps users to choose the most appropriate SST product for their application according to data quality, and applicability (User guide [UGU]):

<https://www.ghrsst.org/files/download.php?m=documents&f=111011142708-GHRSSSTUserGuidev9.pdf>.

Overview tables listing the GHRSSST products, sorted by RDAC are at: <http://www.nodc.noaa.gov/SatelliteData/ghrsst/accessdata.html>, with product information accompanying each product.

When users have decided on the SST product to use, they will require:

- Links to data mining and data visualization tools, matchup datasets, and software (see the User Guide, <https://www.ghrsst.org/data/ghrsst-data-tools/> and the tutorial at LTSRF).
- News and service messages, with automatic and selective near-real time sending (<https://www.ghrsst.org/news/>).
- Frequently Asked Questions and User Forum (at GDAC).
- Operational messages (<https://www.ghrsst.org/data/operational-announcements/>).
- Characterization and further links about relevant SST related Science (see GHRSSST sub-group pages, enter via <https://www.ghrsst.org/ghrsst-science/science-team-groups/>).

4.2 User guidance requirement

For instance, the general users need pointing to and explanations of the different SSTs: skin, sub-skin, bulk and foundation SST. The users need clear definitions, and explanations. For instance, that long temporal scale applications might best served with foundation temperature and bulk temperature in some cases. The short temporal scale applications (meteorological, air-sea flux) require skin and sub-skin temperatures, too. The issue of diurnal variability should be brought to the attention of the users, and the wind stress and wave mixing which matter for the diurnal profile.

Also, users should be pointed to geostationary orbit for high temporal resolution, and polar orbit for high spatial resolution and high accuracy (albeit limited coverage).

The users need to be provided with the knowledge that Microwave can see through non-precipitating cloud and IR fails over cloud and heavy aerosol load, and varying water vapour content (tropics, high latitudes). The users need explanations on which retrieval methods take the latter into account. If relevant for them, they can be pointed to the HL-TAG and CDR-TAG pages for further information.

For interpreting SST gradients, user should be aware of different methods used for data-merging (and contact IC-TAG for more information)

Longer-term applications should be pointed reanalysis products and ongoing CDR-TAG activities.

For information on uncertainty information, and especially for combination with in-situ observations, users should refer ST-VAL.

5 Sources of User Requirements

5.1 GHR SST Science Team

Requirements for SST GHR SST have been sourced from GHR SST Science Team members and attendees at GHR SST Science Team meetings. These are split into five broad categories:

- Coastal/Inland Seas (Ultra-high <4km resolution requirement)
- Open Ocean
- Operational forecasting systems (NWP/Oceans)
- Climate research and Seasonal Forecasting
- Science (Oceanography/Meteorology)

Coastal/Inland Seas users are defined as those using SST data products in specific regional areas and experiments. Typically, this user group has a requirement for "ultra-high-resolution" SST data sets (1-2 km spatial resolution and <6 hours temporal resolution) with good accuracy (<0.3K) and temporal coverage (hourly). Ancillary information that can be used to interpret/complement/quality control the SST data are extremely useful.

Open Ocean users are defined as those using SST data products extending over ocean basins or the entire global ocean. Typically, this user group has a requirement for good accuracy (<0.3K), moderate spatial resolution of <10 km 12-24 hours' temporal resolution. Ancillary information that can be used to interpret/complement/quality control the SST data are extremely useful.

Operational users may be interested in both the Coastal Seas and Open Ocean but have a requirement for operational (24 hour guaranteed data delivery) in real time. Timeliness is a major issue as any data that arrives at the forecasting centre after the forecast model has been run is of much less use. Data should be at the centre within 6 hours of acquisition, good accuracy (<0.3K) and spatial resolution of between 5-10 km. Uncertainty estimates are required for each measurement. Note that the next generation of NWP and Ocean forecast systems are expected to require even higher spatial resolution data sets in some regions. Ancillary information that can be used to interpret and quality control the SST data are extremely useful.

Climate Research users are concerned with only the most accurate data that is available. There are no timeliness constraints and typically, fairly coarse spatial resolution data sets are all that is required (although this is expected to change in the future). A time series of >10 years is the minimum length for a climate data set with accuracies of better than 0.1K. Stability of the time-series is an extremely important issue and stabilities of 0.01K per decade are called for. Ancillary information that can be used to quality control and help interpret the SST data are useful.

See the recent CDR-TAG draft of SST climate record requirements for a comprehensive characterization. Scientific users are those groups interested in developing new tools and methods for the generation of GHR SST data products. They include those interested in SST validation, bias correction methods, analysis algorithms, analysis method development etc. Typically, this user group requires access to the highest spatial and temporal resolution SST data products which high accuracy in a format that is easy to work with. Ancillary information that can be used to help interpret and quality control the SST data are extremely useful.

5.2 NASA Interim Sea Surface Temperature Science Team

The NASA Interim SST Science Team requirements are shown in Table 5-1.

Application	Spatial resolution (Km)	Temporal resolution (hrs)	Geolocation accuracy (Km)	Absolute accuracy (K)	Relative accuracy
CDR				0.1	0.04 ⁰ K/decade
CDR					0.05 ⁰ K/decade
NWP	5	3		0.3	
Global Operations	0.25	3	0.1	0.1	0.05 ⁰ K
Coastal/Lake Operations	0.1	6	0.1	0.1	
Fronts	0.1	0.25	0.1	1	0.1 ⁰ K
Climate Models	25	24	5	0.2	0.05 ⁰ K
Lakes	1	3	1	0.3	0.2 ⁰ K
Air-sea fluxes	10	24	2	0.1	
Mesoscale	1	168		0.1	0.1 ⁰ K
Submesoscale	0.1	24		0.1	0.1 ⁰ K
Strictest	01	0.25	0.1	0.1	0.05 ⁰ K 0.04 ⁰ K/decade

Table 5-1: Requirements for SST error budget as collected in the Sea Surface Temperature Error Budget: White Paper NASA Interim Sea Surface Temperature Science Team (ISSTST) White Paper.

5.3 User requirements collected by the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO)

The World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) maintains a list of user requirements, gathered by the WMO, the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) and the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) organisations. The requirements for SST are shown in the Tables below, from [URL-2].

Application Area	Uncert. Thresh	HR Thresh	OC Thresh	Avail Thresh	Source
ACSYS	2 K	100 km	2 d	60 d	WCRP
Climate - GOOS	1 K	300 km	30 d	30 d	GOOS JPO
Climate-AOPC	1 K	500 km	24 h	12 h	AOPC
Climate-OOPC	0.2 K	500 km	24 h	12 h	OOPC
CLIVAR	0.3 K	50 km	6 h	3 d	WCRP
Global Modelling	2 K	250 km	12 h	60 d	WCRP
Global NWP	1 K	250 km	5 d	5 d	John Eyre
High Res NWP	1 K	20 km	6 h	6 h	JF Mahfouf
Marine biology	0.5 K	5 km	2 d	7 h	GOOS JPO
Marine biology	0.5 K	50 km	2 d	7 h	GOOS JPO
Nowcasting	2 K	50 km	6 h	2 h	ET ODRRGOS
Ocean Applications	1 K	100 km	24 h	6 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	1 K	25 km	24 h	6 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.5 K	100 km	24 h	3 d	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.5 K	25 km	3 d	3 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	1 K	10 km	3 h	6 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.5 K	10 km	24 h	3 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean surface - GOOS	2 K	10 km	12 h	4 h	GOOS JPO
SIA	0.5 K	250 km	12 h	24 h	Laura Ferranti
Synoptic Meteorology	2 K	50 km	24 h	24 h	ET ODRRGOS

Application Area	Uncertain Breakthr	HR Breakthr	OC Breakthr	Avail Breakthr	Source
ACSYS	0.794 K	39.7 km	30.2 h	37.8 d	WCRP
Climate - GOOS	0.215 K	31.1 km	29.6 h	29.6 h	GOOS JPO
Climate-AOPC	0.4 K	50 km	6 h	6 h	AOPC
Climate-OOPC	0.126 K	8 km	3 h	5 h	OOPC
CLIVAR	0.2 K	20 km	4 h	36 h	WCRP
Global Modelling	1 K	100 km	3 h	45 d	WCRP
Global NWP	0.5 K	15 km	24 h	24 h	John Eyre
High Res NWP	0.5 K	5 km	2 h	60 min	JF Mahfouf
Marine biology	0.2 K	2 km	36 h	4 h	GOOS JPO
Marine biology	0.2 K	20 km	36 h	4 h	GOOS JPO

Nowcasting	0.794 K	10.8 km	108 min	78 min	ET ODRRGOS
Ocean Applications	0.5 K	25 km	3 h	60 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.5 K	10 km	3 h	60 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.2 K	50 km	3 h	24 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.2 K	10 km	24 h	2 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.5 K	1 km	60 min	60 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.2 K	5 km	12 h	2 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean surface - GOOS	0.271 K	2.2 km	7.6 h	2.5 h	GOOS JPO
SIA	0.171 K	85.5 km	6 h	6 h	Laura Ferranti
Synoptic Meteorology	0.794 K	10.8 km	6 h	2.9 h	ET ODRRGOS

Table C3 - WHO Goal					
Application Area	Uncert. Goal	HR Goal	OC Goal	Avail Goal	Source
ACSYS	0.5 K	25 km	24 h	30 d	WCRP
Climate - GOOS	0.1 K	10 km	6 h	6 h	GOOS JPO
Climate-AOPC	0.25 K	10 km	3 h	3 h	AOPC
Climate-OOPC	0.1 K	1 km	60 min	3 h	OOPC
CLIVAR	0.1 K	10 km	3 h	24 h	WCRP
Global Modelling	0.5 K	50 km	60 min	30 d	WCRP
Global NWP	0.3 K	5 km	3 h	3 h	John Eyre
High Res NWP	0.3 K	1 km	60 min	30 min	JF Mahfouf
Marine biology	0.1 K	1 km	24 h	3 h	GOOS JPO
Marine biology	0.1 K	10 km	24 h	3 h	GOOS JPO
Nowcasting	0.5 K	5 km	60 min	60 min	ET ODRRGOS
Ocean Applications	0.1 K	10 km	60 min	4.8 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.1 K	1 km	60 min	4.8 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.1 K	10 km	60 min	12 h	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.1 K	5 km	6 h	60 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.1 K	0.5 km	30 min	30 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean Applications	0.1 K	1 km	3 h	60 min	Ali Mafimbo (JCOMM)
Ocean surface - GOOS	0.1 K	1 km	6 h	2 h	GOOS JPO
SIA	0.1 K	50 km	3 h	3 h	Laura Ferranti
Synoptic Meteorology	0.5 K	5 km	3 h	60 min	ET ODRRGOS

Tables C1, C2 and C3: Requirements on horizontal resolution, observing cycle, timeliness and accuracy of SST data for different user categories, as documented in the WMO Database of Observational Requirements (<http://www.wmo.int/pages/prog/sat/Databases.html>). T/H: the "threshold" is the minimum requirement to be met to ensure that data are useful. Goal: the "goal" is an ideal requirement above which further improvements are not necessary. B/T: the "breakthrough" is an intermediate level between "threshold" and "goal" which, if achieved, would result in a significant improvement for the targeted application.

Threshold: the limit at which the observation becomes ineffectual and is no use for the application.

Breakthrough: the level at which a significant improvement in this application would be achieved.

Objective: the maximum performance limit for the observation, beyond which no significant improvement in the application would be achieved.

5.4 ESA CCI and Climate Modelling User Group (CMUG) requirements

The ESA CCI User Requirement Document collected in high detail the requirements of climate users, this Appendix contains material cited from [CCI]:

The climate modelling user group (CMUG) was established by the ESA to provide links between the CCI projects that will generate data and climate modelling users. Part of their remit is to determine climate modellers' user requirements for each of the ECVs. The requirements they have determined for SST are shown in Table 5-2: Requirements for SST gathered by the CMUG (from Climate Modelling User Group Requirement Baseline Document, v1.2, Sept 2010). (reproduced from Climate Modelling User Group Requirement Baseline Document, v1.2, Sept 2010).

	Horizontal resolution (km)	Observing cycle (hours)	Precision (°C)	Accuracy (°C)	Stability (°C/decade)
Analysis	1	3	0.2	0.4	N/A
CDR	1	3	0.05	0.1	0.1

Table 5-2: Requirements for SST gathered by the CMUG (from Climate Modelling User Group Requirement Baseline Document, v1.2, Sept 2010).

From the ESA CCI Technical Notes [CCN], below the conclusions drawn for the long-term SST products are cited:

The spatial resolution/grid spacing exceeds the breakthrough requirement for all data levels. For level 2 data: the breakthrough requirement is 0.05° and the product will be 4 km; for levels 3 and 4: the breakthrough requirement is 0.1° and the product will be 0.05°.

The frequency of data meets threshold requirements for level 2 and 4 data and the breakthrough requirement for level 3. For level 2 and 3 data: breakthrough requirements are 6 hourly and day/night observations respectively and in both cases the product data files will contain single orbits and so day/night data in a single file; for level 4 the data will represent daily averages against a breakthrough requirement of 12 hourly.

When asked the times that they would like the SSTs for, there was a clear tendency to choose times at 6 hourly intervals (i.e. midnight, 6 a.m. etc.) for level 2 data and 3 hourly intervals for level 3 and 4 data, and for the SSTs to correspond to the same universal time. However, this is a poor match to the observing system. The product plan is to adjust all SSTs to 10.30 am or pm local time.

Users require that the temporal coverage of the product be at least 10 years for level 2 data or 20 years for level 3 and 4; this is comparable to the length of the proposed product, which will span 1991 – 2010 (just under 20 years). There is however a clear requirement for data records of longer than 30 years.

The proposed depths that the SSTs will correspond to (skin SST and 20 cm SST) together will satisfy a high proportion of potential users of the level 2 data (77% of the data sample analysed in this study) but a lower proportion for level 3 data (24%); the level 4 data will correspond to 20 cm depth, which is the joint second most popular choice in the data sample, chosen by 29%.

The decision to provide SST in regions partially covered by sea ice is supported by the analysis of user requirements presented in this document.

The majority of respondents to the questionnaire require global spatial coverage. The most common response at the threshold requirement level is for temporal coverage of one year (24% of responses). However, temporal coverage of 10 years and >30 years received almost as many responses (22% and 21% respectively). At the breakthrough and objective requirement levels there is a clear requirement for data records longer than 30 years. Backwards compatibility with older data is extremely important. Potential users want to be able to use data before the satellite era but also want to take advantage of the SST_cci products, so it is important that the two are consistent.

A timely flow of data on essential climate variables is needed by climate monitoring and analysis centres. The most common requirements for timeliness of data delivery were: longer than a year (threshold); within a year (breakthrough) and within a month (objective). However, some respondents to the questionnaire have much tighter requirements and some need data as quickly as within half a day. Where a preference was specified,

the most common requirements for reliability of data delivery were 75% (threshold) and >99% (breakthrough and objective). There is a continuing need for climate quality data; this can be addressed by ensuring that the data record is extendable in the future when new instrumentation is available. Conversion of the system from research to operational use needs to be promoted, for example by converging climate requirements with operational requirements. Prototype products need to be updated while operationalisation is being set up. When asked how often they would like data to be updated with improvements questionnaire respondents most commonly selected 'continuous incremental updates' (28% of responses). A second peak in the distribution of responses occurred at 'once a year' (23%).

Uncertainties need to be characterised fully, including the full error budget of the translation from the input data to the products. This needs to be improved relative to current datasets. The uncertainties need to accompany the products. Confidence in uncertainty estimates needs to be stated. Uncertainty characteristics should be verified by comparison against independent observations. An estimate of total uncertainty (root mean square of the total error distribution) is most commonly required by questionnaire respondents. Additional uncertainty information such as confidence intervals, systematic uncertainty, random uncertainty, stability and probability distributions are useful to a significant proportion of respondents. Where confidence intervals are provided, there is a clear preference for the 95% confidence interval. Information about the correlation structure of errors is essential or desirable for most respondents. Some potential users need uncertainty information in the form of realisations that efficiently sample the uncertainties (of the order ten realisations to match the size of ensembles that are run). Quality information is needed for each SST value that is simple to use, such as a single field indicating "good/bad" or the overall probability that a value is bad.

Data need to be easily accessible, free and unrestricted. Standards should be followed for data storage and information sharing, in order to reduce operating costs. Access to data, products and documentation needs to be provided and version control should be instigated. It is beneficial to users to reduce as much as possible any barriers to obtaining and using data. Questionnaire respondents have widely varying capabilities in the size of individual files (responses range between <100 KB and >10 GB) and datasets (responses between <100 MB and >10 TB) that they can handle. The requirements of users with access to the least developed computing infrastructures need to be addressed. Standards and procedures for storage of metadata should be developed. A majority (64%) of respondents require data in CF-compliant NetCDF format. Within that majority 12% specified the Group for High Resolution SST (GHRSSST) GDS2.0 standard. When presented with a range of options for obtaining data, respondents most commonly selected FTP (47%), followed by a webpage (28%), an interactive map (11%), OPeNDAP (7%) and DVD (5%). Requests from users for support need to be dealt with quickly and thoroughly by experts [CCI].

All steps taken during product development including algorithm selection and statements about accuracy, resolution and homogeneity should be published. Full information about input data and any processing applied needs to be archived to allow future reprocessing. There is a requirement to publish information about data and algorithm maturity (for example which parts have undergone peer-review), and to say point by point which GCOS guidelines have been followed. The most common service that potential users wish to have provided is the provision of simple documentation to allow them to get started with the data [CCI].

SST_{skin} is the depth most commonly required by respondents, followed by SSTs at depths roughly corresponding to the range of traditional in situ observations (20 cm and 5 m). Reporting of SST is most commonly required for sea-ice affected areas, although 38% of respondents expressing a requirement favoured either ice surface or radiometric temperature [CCI].

Analyses with 10 km or finer spatial resolution and daily or more frequent temporal resolution are required for the number of questionnaire respondents considering these characteristics as strengths of the data to strongly outweigh the number viewing them as weaknesses. Overall, the modes of responses for spatial resolution were 1° (threshold), 0.1° (breakthrough) and <1 km (objective). Data need to be available on different resolutions so it is not necessary for users to re-grid the data themselves; the ability to select the time period is also needed. The most common requirements for data frequency at a location are monthly (threshold), daily (breakthrough) and 3 hourly (objective). However, there are also significant numbers of respondents who have more stringent requirements. For the majority of respondents, it is acceptable to use temporal averaging when building datasets, but it is not acceptable for a significant minority. SSTs are most commonly required at midnight, 6 am, midday and 6pm; additional data at midpoints between those times are required by many, and SSTs at half hour spacing would be used for some applications. Potential users require the diurnal cycle to be resolved. Annual averages/climatologies are required [CCI].

The most common acceptable levels of bias were 0.1 and 0.3°C (threshold), and 0.1°C (breakthrough and objective). The most common response was that 0.1°C is the required level of precision. At the threshold, breakthrough, and objective requirement levels, 0.1°C per decade was the most common response for the

acceptable level of drift. However, a significant number of respondents have stricter requirements, particularly at the breakthrough and objective levels. At the threshold, breakthrough and objective requirement levels the most common response for the acceptable drift in relative bias between day and night SSTs is 0.1°C per decade. Again, many users have stricter requirements. At all requirement levels, the most common response was that 0.1°C per decade is the acceptable change in bias over the annual cycle. The most common requirement is that all of the above should be demonstrated over a spatial scale of 100 km. Potential users require independent validation/verification by a separate [independent] group [CCI].

Data should be combined where this will allow weaknesses in individual datasets to be overcome. By making available single-sensor records, sensor-series datasets, and multiple-sensor analyses, the needs of different users can be met [CCI].

The most common requirement is for level 4 (analysed) data (52%). However, some respondents require level 2 (on native swath or grid, 19%) and level 3 (regridded) data (32%). Respondents have a clear preference that level 3 and level 4 data should be provided on a regular latitude-longitude grid. SST data corresponding to the same universal time is preferred to SSTs at the same local time by the majority of potential users of the SST_cci products. Versions of the data containing gaps (if they exist) and versions without gaps should be provided [CCI].

Cloud location and sea ice locations are the most commonly required additional fields. Some questionnaire respondents also want aerosol, sun glint and rain locations, information about phase and amplitude of the diurnal cycle, information adjustments applied to the data and uncertainties in those adjustments, information about atmospheric humidity and the number of pieces of information used to estimate each SST in the data files. Inclusion of ancillary fields for sea ice concentration and wind speed is wanted by most (60% and 69% respectively) respondents. Some respondents are interested in having aerosol optical depth ancillary fields. Heat flux components, irradiance, cloud properties, amount of rain and fraction of land in a grid cell are also relevant to some respondents [CCI].

The tools that questionnaire respondents most commonly want data creators to provide are for extracting data on different grids, for data reading and subsetting, and for visualisation/evaluation of uncertainty and quality information. Respondents would prefer that code for these tools is open source. The most common choice of language for a dedicated software library is MATLAB (chosen by 34% of respondents), followed by IDL and Fortran (both 14%) [CCI].

For most questionnaire respondents, the following features of the data were either essential or preferable (most essential/preferable first): uncertainty estimates for each SST, verification against independent data, peer-reviewed publication, meta-data describing data sources & processing, discovery metadata, commitment to operational production, diurnal variability information, independence from in situ measurements, and error statistics for a particular region [CCI].

The exhaustive ESA CCI survey captured many more user requirements, in surplus to the usual temporal and spatial resolution, namely the type of SST and quality parameters according to spatial scale, and additional information required. The responses with respect to fields of application [CCI] are shown below using the following colour coding:

- Other
- Clouds
- Dataset production
- High latitude modelling
- Coastal oceanography
- Ocean biology or chemistry
- Atmospheric reanalysis
- Ocean reanalysis
- Climate variability
- Monitoring of climate
- Detection and attribution of climate change
- Decadal forecasting
- Seasonal forecasting
- Regional modelling
- Climate model evaluation
- Climate model initialisation

Figure 5-1: Colours used for each application category [CCI].

Figure 5-2: Depths that SSTs should correspond to [CCI].

Respondents were then queried about the depth of SST that was most useful for their applications. A range of responses were received, as shown in Figure 5-3. Even within application categories there were no clear preferences. Overall, SST_{skin}, which is the depth sensed by infrared satellite instruments, had the most responses [CCI].

Spatial scale for requirements

Figure 5-3: Requirements for precision [CCI].

Figure 5-4 shows preferences for how quality information should be communicated.

Figure 5-4: Preferences for how quality information should be communicated [CCI].

A roughly equal number of respondents chose to either have a binary good/bad flag for each SST value or to have a value for each SST to say the probability that it is bad. Other options, such as providing information about the quality control checks that had been failed, received fewer responses [CCI].

Figure 5-5: Additional information that should be provided in data files [CCI].

Information about cloud and sea ice locations were most commonly selected. However, all the options received a significant number of responses. Additionally, the number of pieces of information used to estimate the SST value was suggested as worthy of inclusion [CCI].

6 How user requirements are addressed within GHRSSST

Within GHRSSST, there is substantial overlap and collaboration between 'science users' and 'operational users'. Thus, within GHRSSST the most stringent user requirements are called for and tested in the ongoing work.

The 'science users' are those groups interested in developing new tools and methods for the generation of GHRSSST data products. They include those interested in SST validation, bias correction methods, analysis algorithms, analysis method development etc. Typically, they require access to the highest spatial and temporal resolution SST data products. Ancillary information is used to help interpreting and quality controlling the SST data.

Spatial and temporal resolution requirements are addressed within AI-TAG. Uncertainty information is estimated in the EV-TAG. Stability is investigated in the AI-TAG and CDR-TAG. Improvements in data quality, as well as in the uncertainty estimation are elaborated within all groups, using independent in-situ data, additional ice and cloud data, or by improving the SST algorithms and making use of the newest development of diurnal variability models.

User service requirements are cared for by the UDS-TAG in a user-friendly data and meta-data provision, and also provides user guidance. A user help desk and a forum is run at the GDAC (at PO-DAAC), contact: Jorge.Vazquez@jpl.nasa.gov. The GHRSSST Project Office disseminates user guidance through the internet: www.ghrsst.org.

7 Summary of user requirements

Operational systems require timely, accurate, reliable and robust SST products in consistent, well-described formats. Climate monitoring and research generally require less timely but more accurate and stable SST products. For other applications (such as fishing, boating, surfing, search and rescue, and oil spill management), spatial coverage and accurate location of ocean features may be more important than SST accuracy or stability.

A summary of target requirements of each user group is summarised in Table 7-1.

Application	Horizontal Resolution (km)	Temporal Resolution (hours)	Delivery Timeliness (hours)	Accuracy (°C)	Stability (°C/yr)
Numerical Weather Prediction - Global - Regional	5 1	24 < 6	3 < 1	0.3 0.3	- -
Ocean Forecasting - Coastal Ocean - Open Ocean	< 1 5 - 10	< 6 < 6	1 1	< 0.1 < 0.1	- -
Seasonal and Interannual Forecasting	10 100	24 24	24 24	< 0.1 < 0.25	0.01
Climate Monitoring and Research	100	24	1 month	0.1	0.01
Coral Reef Management Systems	< 1	1 and 24	24	< 0.3	0.01
Fisheries	< 1	1 and 24	< 3	0.5	-
Coastal and Inland Waters	< 1	1 and 24	1	< 0.3	-
Recreational	< 1	24	1	0.5	-

Table 7-1: Summary of key applications and their SST target requirements.

8 Evolving User Interaction

Within GHRSSST, the Project Office and the AUS-TAG hold special responsibilities for user interaction. The data producing centres have their own and very important communication pathways with the users. GHRSSST data providers are encouraged to provide a short description advertising their data. GHRSSST as a whole plans to serve its users with documents for user guidance, data miners and data access tools, as well as free code for reading data into common programs (Fortran, C, IDL, Matlab)

User feedback is collected via the GPO and the GDAC, the latter is committed to maintain a catalogue of user questions and answers, and a forum for users.

User Requirements are compiled in collaboration with the users, resulting in an annually updated User Requirement Document by GPO.

8.1 User, Data and Services Technical Advisory Group (UDS-TAG)

One of the main goal of the UDS-TAG is to facilitate usage of GHRSSST products across a broad user spectrum. In addition to answering the user questions directly on an individual basis, UDS-TAG also maintains the GHRSSST User's Manual, including data access and descriptions. Another responsibility of the UDS-TAG is to maintain and develop methods for data discovery.

Users of GHRSSST data continue to increase in number. With the emergence of the historically reanalyzed products, there has been a significant increase in using GHRSSST data for scientific research. Near-real time capabilities continue to emerge, specifically in numerical weather forecasting and fisheries. Challenges still remain which must be addressed for maximizing the use of GHRSSST data. In response to these challenges, new tools are implemented to allow for Level 2 and Level 3 sub-setting capabilities at the GDAC. Additional tools such as the THREDDS (Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services) are being implemented to allow users to aggregate data sets with a large number of files. The State of the Ocean (SOTO) near real time visualization tool allows for overlaying different parameters that includes SST and other parameters such as sea surface height. The GDAC maintains a GHRSSST forum which allows users and science team members to interact efficiently on science and technical issues. The GDAC also plans to incorporate tables that will allow users to quickly decide on what data set best fits their usage.

The plan is to optimize and add to the already existing facilities (User Guide, User Forum, Example Code, Data Mining portals).

8.2 GPO user interaction plans

The GHRSSST Project Office interacts directly with users. It maintains connections with the SST power users, directs user questions to the respective experts and plans to ensure user involvement in the GHRSSST annual meetings. The GPO plans to publish and to update user relevant documents and keeps the web-site interesting for users.

8.3 Science Team user interaction

GHRSSST recognises that users need to be pointed to the research relevant to their application by experts. GHRSSST plans to develop "environmental intelligence" which is more than simply supplying environmental data and forecasts. For certain applications, and for choosing the optimum data, users need to be made aware of how the SST data were generated, which feature resolution can be expected, what quality flags and auxiliary information need to be regarded for the correct interpretation. In future, it will become important to be able to explain to stakeholders the significance, uncertainty and science behind the data, particularly with regards to climate data and forecasts. Better education regarding the choice, interpretation and application of SST products is envisaged for the next decade.

1.1 Activities for Evolving User Interaction and Requirements

Action
IV-1 Develop and maintain user friendly tools for data access and analysis
IV-2 Maintain user forum and FAQ catalogue
IV-3 Create material for User guidance
IV-4 Collect User requirements

Table 8-1: Activities to evolve user interaction and requirements

9 Strengthening international collaboration and promotion of GHRSSST

9.1 GHRSSST and the CEOS SST Virtual Constellation

The CEOS Virtual Constellation on SST (SST-VC) shall support the coordination consolidation and further development of satellite SST capability, products, user feedback and education/outreach activities using the recognized and well established GHRSSST as the prime implementation mechanism. Initially SST-VC group members will be those representing CEOS Agencies, the GHRSSST Science Team Chair and selected members of the GHRSSST Science Team involved in relevant SST activities. The emphasis on this structure is to reduce duplication between the successful and functioning work of GHRSSST (as an implementer of the SST-VC) and the SST-VC representing the co-ordination activities of the Agencies.

9.2 Engagement with in situ communities

To maintain the high quality of the satellite SST products provided by GHRSSST it is essential that the group has access to in situ ocean surface data provided by a range of accurate instruments located on diverse platforms, over a wide range of climate conditions. In order to attain this goal GHRSSST will continue and enhance its engagement with the following groups:

- 1 JCOMM Observations Programme Area Coordination Group (OCG) (see <https://www.ghrsst.org/files/download.php?m=documents&f=110524144221-GHRSSSTSubmissionJCOMMOCG4revised.doc>)
- 2 JCOMM Ship Observations Team (SOT) (see Ian Barton's presentation: <https://www.ghrsst.org/documents/q/category/ghrsst-science-team-meetings/ghrsst-xii-edinburgh/ghrsstxii-presentations/breakout-sessions-2011/stval-breakout/>)
- 3 JCOMM Data Buoy Coordination Panel (DBCP) (see <https://www.ghrsst.org/ghrsst-science/science-team-groups/stval-wg/dbcp-ghrsst-pilot-project/>)
- 4 OceanSITES Science Steering Team
- 5 Argo Science Team (see <http://www.ghrsst.org/documents.htm?parent=852>)

Concerning point 2, the following specific recommendations from GHRSSST in relation to in-situ observations were included in the GHRSSST Recommendations to JCOMM OCG document (<https://www.ghrsst.org/files/download.php?m=documents&f=110524144221-GHRSSSTSubmissionJCOMMOCG4revised.doc>) and presented to both the Sixth Meeting of the IOC/UNESCO JCOMM Ship Observations Team SOT-VI - dealing with ship observations only (11-15 April 2011) and the Fourth Session of the JCOMM Observations Coordination Group - OCG-IV dealing with all ocean observation platforms (18-20 April 2011):

- a. Adding the provision of radiometric skin SST data to the JCOMM OCG portfolio of VOS measurements. Ships that participate in such a measurement programme should also maintain a radiosonde capability.
- b. Ensure that ships and other platforms currently providing high quality in situ data where possible expand their provision of meteorological meta-data. Wind speed, history of wind speed, air temperature and local humidity are the most important. Measurements of near-surface temperature profiles should also be encouraged.
- c. Enhance the capability of Argo floats, drifting buoys and moorings to measure temperature profiles in the top 2 meters of the ocean.
- d. Where possible a regular accurate calibration of in situ data instrumentation is carried out, preferably against a standard that is traceable to an SI measurement.
- e. Establishing a JCOMM SOT working group to collaborate with GHRSSST to better define requirements for measurements of SST from ships, and to identify new opportunities that may assist with a more uniform coverage of the global oceans.
- f. Planning to obtain ship of opportunity participation in future SST measurement inter-comparison experiments.
- g. Encourage JCOMM data providers to use the GHRSSST data set to assess the accuracy and performance of their SST measurement instruments.

Concerning point 3, a pilot project in collaboration with DBCP has started to improve pre-and post-deployment sensor calibration, improved sensor installation and additional meta-data. The progress of this pilot project is monitored by ST-VAL, see: <https://www.ghrsst.org/ghrsst-science/science-team-groups/stval-wg/dbcp-ghrsst-pilot-project/>.

Concerning point 5, GHRSSST recommended to Argo a specification of vertical resolution of 10 cm from 0 to 3 m and 50 cm resolution from 4m to 10 m. In addition to the diurnal warming studies the Argo near surface profiles allow, GHRSSST recognises the special value of Argo as an independent in-situ reference system.

9.3 GHRSSST Promotion and Capacity building through the GPO

Promotion objectives are to: 1) present information to users, potential users, scientists, space agencies, national and international funding bodies, and to the general public, 2) to increase demand for GHRSSST data and to 3) differentiate the GHRSSST products with respect to usage from each other, and from non-GHRSSST products.

Media of GHRSSST promotion include: the web-site with GHRSSST News service, emails, brochures, conference attendance and collaboration in shared projects.

Promoting GHRSSST to users: Promoting GHRSSST will be pursued by attending conferences, and encouraging all GHRSSST members to do similarly. First priority are conferences where power users are (related to Operational Ocean Forecasting, Numerical Weather prediction, Climate Science, Oceanography, Remote Sensing Community, Space agencies).

The network of people with access to GHRSSST news will be planned to increase. This way, reminders on GHRSSST are paired with useful information. More GHRSSST news are aimed to advertise new products, or advances in GHRSSST related science.

Promoting GHRSSST to scientists: International collaboration and in fact many personal overlaps with ERNESST and NASA SST Science Team will ensure highest level of research is maintained and fostered.

The best advertisement for GHRSSST is the highly valued data GHRSSST provides to the users. This should be eased as much as possible by convenient data access, and a broad presence of references to GHRSSST.

Promoting GHRSSST to data producers: A strong relationship with GHRSSST users and scientists will make GHRSSST attractive to the data producers. Sometimes, new data producers are approached when new satellite instruments have been successfully launched, as the new producers would greatly benefit from the GHRSSST potential.

Existing data producers will be approached when necessary for discussion about potential national limitations on distributing data.

Contact with data producers will be via CEOS-VC (when CEOS-SST-VC is in place), GOOS, Space agencies and National Research bodies and Met Services.

Promoting GHRSSST to national and international programs, space agencies and funding bodies: By establishing contact and informing about the progress of GHRSSST in terms of data production, standardization, GHRSSST data usage, GHRSSST user support, science and achievements in defining community best practices.

Promoting GHRSSST to the public (interested laymen): Through webpages and brochures

Capacity building in GHRSSST: Generally, capacity building refers to the concept as actions that enhance an organizations ability to work towards its mission, which is for GHRSSST: "*To develop and nurture cooperation and progress at the world scale in the subject area of satellite Sea Surface Temperature*", as has been agreed by the GHRSSST Science Team at the 9th International GHRSSST Science Team meeting, Perros Guirrec, June, 2008.

Capacity development in GHRSSST: Special emphasis will be given in GHRSSST to develop the Community Capacity which brings benefits in terms of:

- the increase in skills and competencies on the part of members of such communities;
- gain from synergies, research crossfertilization, knowledge transfer and collaboration
- the more effective, efficient and sustainable delivery of services

- increase in sustainability of the GHRSSST service, and quality assurance of GHRSSST data

Capacity building (users, scientists, producers): Capacity building will be started by expanding national contacts to span the majority of the global groups. Currently, the US, the UK, and France are well incorporated within GHRSSST. Special effort goes to foster relations with Japan and South American groups, follow up the link to Korean groups and to build up links with China and India. Currently missing links to, for example, Canada, Germany and former Eastern Europe and Russia, South Africa, Kenya need investigation. The user statistics of the GHRSSST web site according to country will give clues where to direct activities. Good sources of contact points for new patrons representing missing countries are with GODAE-OceanView, JCOMM, WMO, and the national space agencies.

Plans for capacity building development in new nations: Capacity building includes the development of collaboration with, and transfer of knowledge to, nations not yet involved. In special focus are nations with a strong interest in SST, and with thriving activities in the space observation segment. Contact will be established and common interest and potential for collaboration explored. These groups will be invited to join the GHRSSST activities (collaboration with GHRSSST Technical Advisory Groups, Working Groups, and offer to review of documents, participation in Science Team Meetings and user symposia).

9.4 Activities to Strengthen international collaboration and promotion of GHRSSST

Action
V.1 CEOS-VC SST implementation plan
V.2 Communication of SST user needs to CEOS members
V.3 Maintain links to GHRSSST related international groups
V.4 Influencing bodies responsible for in-situ measurements such as to consider GHRSSST needs
V.5 Communicating quality of upgraded drifters to DBCP
V.6 Communicating the use of Argo near-surface profiles for diurnal model validation, and independent reference source

Table 9-1: Activities to Strengthen international collaboration and promotion of GHRSSST

How to find out more about GHR SST

A complete description of GHR SST together with all project documentation can be found at:

<https://www.ghrsst.org>

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